

TWO LETHAL KILLERS: THE DEVASTATING IMPACT OF *PUCCINIA RECONDITA* AND *PUCCINIA GRAMINIS* ON WHEAT GRAIN WEIGH

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Abstract. In 2024, the 1000 grain weight of most wheat varieties dropped by nearly 25%, strongly correlated with the increased severity of leaf and stem rust infections. Leaf rust disrupts photosynthesis, reducing the plant's ability to produce essential carbohydrates for grain filling. Stem rust further damages stem tissues, impairing nutrient transport, exacerbating the decline in grain weight. Varieties such as Zlata and Altayskaya Zhnitsa were most affected, while Tymenskaya 29 and Uchitel showed better resilience. Additionally, varieties like Tulaykovskaya 108, Favorit, and Synthetic hexaploid wheat (SHW) No.23, No.35, No.65, and No.67 demonstrated strong resistance to both leaf and stem rust, scoring between 7 and 9 points, making them important for sustainable farming practices.

Key words: *triticum aestivum*, leaf rust, stem rust, rust resistance, grain weight.

Introduction

Wheat refers to the cultivated *Triticum* spp., including the most common hexaploid bread wheat (*T. aestivum* L.) and the tetraploid durum wheat (*T. turgidum* var. *durum*). These cereal crops are the staple food in most developing countries and are the most traded grains globally. Wheat rust is among the earliest documented plant diseases, dating back to Aristotle's time (384–322 B.C.) [1]. Leaf rust, and stem rust, caused by *Puccinia triticina*, and sp. *Graminis* respectively, continue to threaten wheat production worldwide. Utilization of resistant cultivars is the most effective and chemical-free strategy to control rust diseases. Conventional and molecular biology techniques identified more than 200 resistance genes and their associated markers from common wheat and wheat wild relatives, which can be used by breeders in resistance breeding programmes. However, there is continuous emergence of new races of rust pathogens with novel degrees of virulence, thus rendering wheat resistance genes ineffective. An integration of genomic selection, genome editing, molecular breeding and marker-assisted selection, and phenotypic evaluations is required in developing high quality wheat varieties with resistance to multiple pathogens. Although host genotype resistance and application of fungicides are the most generally utilized approaches for controlling wheat rusts, effective agronomic methods are required to reduce disease management costs and increase wheat production sustainability [2].

Wheat leaf rust, caused by the fungus *Puccinia recondita*, primarily affects the normal growth and development of wheat by infecting the leaves, which are critical for the plant's photosynthetic processes. The fungus disrupts the chlorophyll in the leaves, reducing the efficiency

of photosynthesis, which in turn diminishes the plant's ability to produce the carbohydrates essential for energy production and growth. This reduction in photosynthetic capacity particularly impacts the grain-filling stage, as the developing grains rely heavily on the sugars and nutrients produced by photosynthesis during this period. As a result, the plant cannot adequately fill the grains, leading to a lower 1000-grain weight and a significant decline in overall yield. In severe cases of infection, the cumulative effects of reduced nutrient transport and energy production can cause considerable losses in wheat productivity, affecting not only the quantity but also the quality of the harvest [3,4].

Wheat stem rust, caused by *Puccinia graminis* is one of the most devastating fungal diseases in wheat production. The disease can lead to wheat production reductions of up to 75%, and some areas even experience no production [5]. Stem rust mainly destroys the tissues of wheat stems and leaves. Its spores can penetrate the leaves, invade the host from the stomata, reduce the photosynthetic area of the host, destroy the guiding tissues of the stems, and hinder nutrient transport [6].

The focus of this research is to assess the susceptibility of these diverse wheat varieties to leaf and stem rust infections, examining how these pathogens reduce the photosynthetic capacity and nutrient translocation in infected plants, ultimately leading to lower grain weights. Understanding how different wheat varieties respond to these two rust pathogens can help in developing strategies to mitigate their devastating effects on global wheat yields.

Materials and methods

The study involved 43 spring wheat varieties of various ecological and geographical origins. These included 14 varieties from Russia, one variety each from Belarus, Austria, and Germany, three varieties from Poland, and 21 synthetic lines from CIMMYT (International Maize and Wheat Improvement Center). The early maturing variety Zlata, developed by the Federal Research Center Nemchinovka, was used as the control standard for comparison. Field research was conducted at the Field Experimental Station of K.A. Timiryazev Russian State Agricultural Academy during the 2021-2024 growing seasons. The experimental plots were organized systematically, with a plot size of 1 m², and each variant was replicated three times. Phenological phases of plant development were monitored throughout the growing season. Disease resistance, specifically against leaf rust (*Puccinia recondita*) and stem rust (*Puccinia graminis*), was assessed using the VIR 9-point (score) scale, a widely recognized scale for evaluating disease susceptibility in crops. On this scale, a rating of 1 represents high susceptibility, while 9 indicates complete immunity. Intermediate ratings of 3, 5, and 7 correspond to increasing levels of resistance, with 3 indicating moderate susceptibility and 7 indicating moderate resistance.

Results and Discussion

The meteorological conditions varied significantly throughout the years of the field trials. In 2021, sowing was delayed until May 11 due to excessive moisture and low temperatures. Although seedlings emerged quickly, the hot and dry weather during grain formation reduced the overall yield (204 mm of precipitation, with a total accumulation of active temperatures reaching 1540°C). In 2022, sowing occurred on May 5 under conditions close to the long-term average. The period from seedling emergence to heading experienced cooler temperatures and sufficient moisture, which extended the growing season (208 mm of precipitation, with a total of 1287°C in active temperatures). In 2023, sowing took place on April 22, with seedlings emerging on May 2. A lack of rainfall during the first half of the growing season negatively impacted plant growth, despite the increase in precipitation during the second half, which was unevenly distributed. In

2024, sowing occurred on April 29, though seedling emergence was delayed until May 14 due to low temperatures. Precipitation in the first half of the season was half that of 2022, but in the second half, rainfall exceeded the average, making the year favorable for evaluating brown rust resistance.

Figure 1. Meteorological conditions during the study years (2021-2024).

In 2024, the 1000 grain weight of most wheat varieties decreased by almost 25%, a decline strongly correlated with the increased severity of leaf and stem rust infections (*Puccinia recondita* and *Puccinia graminis*, respectively). Leaf rust primarily disrupts photosynthesis by infecting the leaves, leading to reduced chlorophyll content and limiting the plant's ability to synthesize essential carbohydrates for growth and grain filling. This inhibition during the critical grain-filling stage results in smaller and underdeveloped grains, which directly contributes to the observed decline in 1000 grain weight in 2024.

Furthermore, stem rust exacerbates the problem by attacking the stem tissues, destroying the conductive pathways necessary for nutrient and water transport. This dual attack from both pathogens disrupts the translocation of essential nutrients, further limiting the plant's capacity to support grain development. These effects, combined, have caused a substantial decrease in grain weight across most varieties.

The study's findings highlight the vulnerability of certain varieties, such as *Zlata* and *Altayskaya Zhnitsa*, which exhibited pronounced decreases in grain weight under high disease pressure in 2024. On the other hand, varieties like *Tymenskaya 29* and *Uchitel* demonstrated relatively better resilience, maintaining a closer grain weight to their 2021-2023 averages, suggesting potential resistance to rust pathogens or better adaptation to environmental stresses.

Figure

2. Comparison of 1000 grain weight (g) of different wheat varieties for the periods 2021-2024 (n: 2021-2023) and 2024 (ys 2024)

In the study conducted during the years 2023 and 2024, the evaluation of various crop varieties and lines for resistance to leaf rust revealed several high-performing candidates. The varieties with the strongest resistance, as indicated by scores ranging between 7 and 9 points, are highlighted below. Tulaykovskaya 108 consistently scored 7 points in both 2023 and 2024, indicating stable resistance over time. Similarly, Favorit exhibited steady performance with a resistance score of 7 in both years. The synthetic line L-57 achieved a score of 7 in 2024, demonstrating its resilience to leaf rust in that year. Among the numbered lines, several showed exceptional resistance. No.23, No.35, No.65, No.67, and No.178 all scored the maximum 9 points in both 2023 and 2024, making them some of the most resistant lines in the study. Additionally, the lines No.59, No.66, No.70, No.147, No.151, No.215, No.221, and No.223 scored 9 points in 2023 and 7 points in 2024, reflecting a slight decline but still maintaining strong resistance over the two years.

In the assessment of stem rust resistance for the year 2024, several varieties and synthetic lines exhibited high resistance, scoring between 7 and 9 points. These varieties demonstrated strong resilience to stem rust, making them valuable for sustainable agricultural practices. Notably, Granova achieved a resistance score of 7 points, reflecting solid resistance, while Canyuk and the synthetic lines No.23, No.35, No.59, No.65, No.67, No.187, and No.221 all scored the maximum 9 points, demonstrating exceptional resistance to stem rust. Other lines, including No.66, No.147, No.215, and No.223, also showed strong resistance with scores of 7 points. These varieties and lines are critical for sustainable farming due to their ability to withstand stem rust, reducing the need for chemical treatments and promoting long-term environmental stability. Their strong performance against this widespread disease underlines their importance in breeding programs aimed at improving crop resilience.

Conclusions

The severity of leaf and stem rust in 2024 caused a notable 25% reduction in the 1000 grain weight across many wheat varieties. These pathogens severely impacted photosynthesis and nutrient transport, leading to significant grain losses, particularly in susceptible varieties like Zlata

and Altayskaya Zhnitsa. In contrast, varieties such as Tymenskaya 29 and Uchitel exhibited stronger resilience, maintaining more stable grain weights. Several varieties and synthetic lines, including Tulaykovskaya 108, Favorit, and No.23, No.35, No.65, and No.67, displayed high levels of resistance to both leaf and stem rust, with scores between 7 and 9 points. These resistant varieties hold promise for future breeding programs aimed at enhancing crop resilience and promoting sustainable agricultural practices.

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